

Management of Human Resources in the Activities of Small Businesses and Micro-Enterprises in Construction

Mukhammadiyev Utkir Akhmedovich

Associate Professor of “Business Management” Department at SamSCU

Dumayev Azizkhon Suvankhan ogli

Graduate Master’s Student of SamSCU

Abstract. The importance of small business and private entrepreneurship in the economy of our country is estimated not only by its contribution to the gross domestic product, but also by its role in providing employment to the population. At the same time, there are problems in the management of human resources in various areas of the real economy. This article is dedicated to revealing special aspects of personnel management in small construction organizations and micro-firms. The authors have developed scientific recommendations for increasing the efficiency of workers.

Key words: human resources, employment, small business, construction, personnel management.

Аннотация. Мамлакатимиз иқтисодиётида кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорликнинг аҳамияти нафақат ялпи ички маҳсулотга қўшган хиссаси, балки кўп жиҳатдан аҳоли бандлигини таъминлашдаги ўрни билан баҳоланади. Шу билан бирга реал иқтисодиётнинг турли соҳаларида инсон ресурсларини бошқаришда муаммолар мавжуд. Мазкур мақола кичик қурилиш ташкилотлари ва микрофирмаларда ходимларни бошқаришнинг алоҳида жиҳатларини очиқ беришга бағишланган. Муаллифлар томонидан ишчилар фаолиятининг самарадорлигини ошириш бўйича илмий тавсиялар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: инсон ресурслари, бандлик, кичик бизнес, қурилиш, ходимларни бошқариш.

Аннотация. В нашей стране значение малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства оценивается не только его вкладом в валовый внутренний продукт, но и, в значительной степени, местом в обеспечении занятости населения. Вместе с тем, в различных реальных отраслях экономики имеются проблемы в управлении человеческими ресурсами. Настоящая статья посвящена раскрытию отдельных аспектов управления персоналом в малых строительных организациях и микрофирмах. Авторами разработаны научные предложения по повышению эффективности деятельности рабочих.

Ключевые слова: человеческие ресурсы, занятость, малый бизнес, строительство, управление персоналом.

Introduction. In the economic development model of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an important place is allocated to small business and private entrepreneurship. Small business not only reveals the entrepreneurial potential of the population, but also has opportunities to compete equally with large organizations in many fields. One such field is the construction field. If we pay attention to statistical data, in 2023, the share of small enterprises and micro-firms in the construction of buildings and structures - 47.0% (49354.4 billion soums), increased by 7.8% compared to the indicator of 2022, the share of large construction organizations - It was 25.2% (26,420.4 billion soums), i.e. 95.4% compared to the indicator of 2022. The share of the third, i.e., the informal sector, is 27.8% and has increased by 5.8% compared to 2022.[1] It is worth noting that the informal sector is also a form of public initiative and can be included in small business.

Similarly, in 2023, the share of construction works performed by large enterprises for the construction of civil facilities was 26.7% and decreased by 4.2% compared to 2022. Also, the share of small enterprises and micro-enterprises was 73.2% (increased by 4.2% points) and the share of the informal sector remained at the level of the 2022 indicator and made 0.1%. [1]

These numbers show the place of small business and private entrepreneurship, and prove the need to pay deeper attention to the problems of increasing the efficiency of this subject of the economy.

Research methodology. The scientific assumption accepted in the ongoing research is based on the feasibility of increasing the socio-economic efficiency of small business by efficient use of human resources. Statistical analysis, scientific reasoning, selective observation, deduction and induction methods were used in the research.

Literature analysis. In recent years in Uzbekistan, especially in the field of construction, the issues of small business development have been focused on in researches of M. Boltaboev, M. Kasimova [2], R.S. Muratov [3], A.A.Abdullaev [4], M.Siddikov [5], I.Usmanov, Kh.Buriev [6].

In these researches, more attention is paid to aspects of state support of small business and private entrepreneurship in construction. Human capital, the main resource of small businesses, has not been given enough attention.

Main part. The results of the analysis of the activities of small businesses and micro-firms in construction can be summarized as follows. Small construction organizations are limited to building one or two objects in a year. As a result, the possibilities of expanding the material and technical base, applying advanced

technologies, and using new materials and techniques are reduced. Directions and measures for solving the above problems by developing small business infrastructure, expanding outsourcing services, and improving financing mechanisms have been developed.

The biggest problem for small businesses in construction in general is the problem of hidden employment. Today, the economic environment formed in the Republic of Uzbekistan has created an opportunity for small enterprises to attract workers to facilities without registration. Under these circumstances, company managers are not interested in increasing the number of permanent employees. At the same time, the increase of one-day employment (labor market in the vernacular) systems is causing unskilled workers to enter the construction market. The head of our country is also very worried about this problem. In the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the selector meeting on January 16, 2024, the following was noted: "For example, 41 percent of construction enterprises indicated only 1 worker in their report. But these enterprises completed construction work worth 4 trillion soums last year alone." [6]

Organizational problems of small construction organizations include:

First, the small size of the construction determines the low demand for construction materials, as a result, the stock management system is in a backward state, there is no need for modern logistics chains, there is no need for the mechanization of loading and unloading operations, there is no need to create a warehouse system, and the advantages of purchasing construction materials at wholesale prices are not used. This causes production costs to be high.

Secondly, the low volumes of construction works, the narrowness of the scope of works at the facility interferes with the specialization of workers, and is an obstacle to their professional and professional growth. A worker with average skills in many professions cannot master a specific profession perfectly. The saddest thing is that over time there is a tendency for workers' skills to decline. In small construction organizations, the system of training of workers is not formed, or only the management personnel are trained. This ultimately has a negative impact on the quality of construction.

Thirdly, performance of management functions in small construction organizations becomes complicated. A business, whether it is large or small, has all the functions of management. Although these functions are simpler in a small enterprise, it is necessary to have specialists with sufficient knowledge to perform them. Due to the small number of key workers, the volume of construction work performed by them will not be enough to provide the administration with funds, in this regard, only the most necessary employees are hired, and some management

functions are assigned to them. As a result, the assignment of several management functions to one person has a negative impact on the quality of management. Studies have shown that highly centralized linear structures are common in small construction organizations for this very reason.

Relying on the world experience of managing small business entities, it may be appropriate to apply the following directions for solving the above problems in small businesses and micro-enterprises in construction. The first direction is to expand the capabilities of small businesses through the development of business infrastructure.

This direction is a method widely used in developed countries, and its content is related to the assignment of tasks not related to the execution of construction works to external organizations. The idea is that if a small enterprise is unable to perform certain tasks, then another organization will perform them on the basis of a contract. Such services are called outsourcing and guarantee competent service. In the field of construction, it is envisaged to outsource accounting and auditing, drawing up a work project, drawing up a business plan, training employees, product certification, testing purchased materials and many other tasks. Considering the large number of small construction organizations in the region, this mechanism can benefit both enterprises and business infrastructure.

We can give an example of the Republican Chamber of Commerce and Industry as an example of organizations that create wide opportunities for outsourcing in construction. Business incubators are also an element of modern infrastructure and are useful partners for newly formed construction organizations.

The second direction of increasing the efficiency of small business activity in construction is related to the creation of new horizontal organizational structures. In today's economy, the mutually beneficial cooperation of various organizations in the form of non-governmental and non-profit organizations is becoming widespread.

Market participants form a new type of information exchange to gain competitive advantage, that is, they create a hub for all. The main task of such organizations is to combine certain tasks and resources. For example, in construction, small enterprises and micro-firms will be able to specialize in only one production line. If the company has 15-20 employees, it is possible to form a maximum of two specialized brigades. In the case of a construction site, the level of specialization should reach at least 10-12, including mechanized work. It should be recognized that there may be more than 20 specializations of brigades in large construction companies.

The creation of an information center for the pooling of resources by small construction firms will serve to solve the problem of providing facilities with qualified labor, as well as creating a work front for their crews.

For example, 20 companies specializing in different areas have jointly formed an information center. In ten of them, the contract for the construction of objects was concluded and the works were started. On the basis of the calendar plan, how many workers are needed in these facilities in what specialization are entered into the database. Based on this, all participants know in which facility there is a shortage of workers. A company in need of workers can subcontract the relevant work front to the relevant brigade of other companies. On the one hand, it ensures the employment of temporarily idle workers, on the other hand, the efficiency of construction works increases, and on the third hand, the quality of products increases through the specialization of construction works.

Conclusion. Today, we can see the low effectiveness of administrative measures in the management of human resources in the construction industry. Based on the above proposals, the creation of mechanisms for voluntary association of small construction organizations, information exchange and creation of information-based horizontal structures will serve to improve the quality and efficiency of the workforce.

References

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти ҳузуридаги Статистика агентлиги расмий сайти.
2. Болтабаев М, Қосимова М. “Кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорлик” 2011 йил. Иқтисод. 126-154 б.б.
3. Р.Муратов, Н.Пулатов. Мамлакат иқтисодиётини модернизация қилиш шароитида кичик бизнес корхоналарини молиялаштириш механизмлари ва истиқболлари. “Иқтисодиёт ва инновацион технологиялар” илмий электрон журнали. № 6, ноябрь-декабрь, 2015 йил.
4. А.Абдуллаев. Қурилиш соҳасида кичик бизнес ва хусусий тадбиркорликнинг ижтимоий-иқтисодий самарадорлигини ошириш стратегияси. Диссертация автореферати, 2019 й.
5. М.Сиддиқов. Қурилишда тадбиркорликни ривожлантиришнинг айрим масалалари. *Iqtisodiyot va ta’lim*, (5), 2021. - 327–331. https://doi.org/10.55439/ECED/vol_iss5/a254
6. И.Усманов, Х.Буриев. Қурилиш соҳасида ташкилотларни бошқаришнинг долзарб масалалари. Архитектура. Қурилиш. Дизайн. Илмий техник журнал. Тошкент. - №4, 2019 йил. – 196-199 бетлар.
7. <https://kun.uz/news/2024/01/16/shavkat-mirziyoyev-tahlillar-onlab-trillion-somlik-mahsulot-soyada-qolayotganini-korsatmoqda>.